

TECHNOLOGY FOR INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the technology of increasing the social activity of teachers. Teaching is about encouraging students to reach their full potential. Although there are many ways to become an experienced pedagogue, this article deals with the process of training and retraining of pedagogues, as well as improving the pedagogical skills of pedagogues, effectively conducting the education and training process in them, and raising their spiritual potential. will be considered.

Keywords: Reason, knowledge, understanding, teaching, method, teacher, process, success, information, technology, technology, skilled, development, progress.

Forming a healthy spiritual environment in educational institutions on the basis of a cultural-humanitarian approach, forming high moral and ethical qualities in future specialists, establishing a new national system of spiritual and moral values, deepening the spiritual and moral heritage. made it possible to learn. deepening, improvement of pedagogical mechanisms of education in the spirit of national pride and pride.

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. 4947 "On the strategy of actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. 2 "On the development of the social sphere" in the fourth direction, measures are being taken to create comfort for the population. improving the quality of general secondary, secondary special and higher education of preschool educational institutions, their development. "Implementation of measures" is intended. These issues are directly related to the correct solution of the issue of spiritual and moral maturity of a person growing up in our society.

In chapter VI of the concept of continuous spiritual and educational education approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the implementation of spiritual and educational education in the general secondary education system is divided into two periods (the first period - 7 It is noted that it is included in paragraph 6). 10-year period - in primary grades; the second period - 11-17 years old - in middle and upper classes).

In the implementation of this task, high professional potential and human qualities are required from each of the pedagogic staff of public educational institutions. At the same time, such qualities are required from teachers. First of all, students have a leading role in the formation of age-appropriate moral and ethical qualities (computations) - loyalty to the Motherland, entrepreneurship, willpower, ideological immunity, kindness, responsibility, tolerance, legal culture, and new thinking.

A teacher should have patriotism and patriotism qualities, love and glorify his motherland from the bottom of his heart, not spare himself for his country, be a master of his profession, a real expert who can mobilize all his abilities in this way. need in this case, it is

necessary to set an example for these students. For this, it is necessary to develop the continuous spiritual potential of pedagogues.

The concept of competence is a concept that initially entered the field of education as a result of psychological and pedagogical research, and is used as a modern term.

"Competence" is derived from the Latin word, and when translated into Uzbek, its dictionary meaning means "a person who knows well", "a person with experience". Therefore, competence is how a pedagogue behaves in various situations and unexpected situations that arise in the educational process, is open to communication, has the ability to understand the mental state of young people, and has a new relationship with competitors. Existing problems in ambiguous tasks mean the ability of a pedagogue to apply the knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired based on specific goals in the use of information full of conflicts, to have an action plan in consistently developing and complex processes.

Improving the quality of education is one of the most urgent problems of the world community today. To solve it, it is necessary to update the content of education, revise the technologies of the educational process and the ultimate goal of education.

Education can be considered as a specially organized process of developing the ability of students to independently solve problems of personal and social importance in various spheres of activity based on mastering the culture of society. Such an understanding of the purpose of education, in turn, lays the groundwork for the implementation of a competent approach.

In the years of independence in Uzbekistan, it was necessary for every person living in this country to understand his identity, to study deeply the heritage of our ancient history and rich culture, great ancestors, and to look at the reality of today with a conscious eye. It is the duty of all pedagogues to change lives, think independently and live with a sense of belonging to all changes in our country.

In this regard, the process of training general secondary education pedagogues and improving their qualifications, improving their pedagogical skills, effectively conducting the educational process, and further improving their spiritual and moral competence is of great scientific and practical importance. In the process of qualification improvement, basic, general and personal competence of the teacher is improved by clarifying pedagogical and psychological features and development level factors, improving pedagogical activities. The process of professional development requires teachers not only to acquire general cultural competences, but also to independently find and use various sources of information related to spiritual and educational activities, to effectively communicate with subjects of spiritual and educational activities. It requires having knowledge, scientific and educational knowledge. The formation of professional competencies such as identifying, analyzing and processing technical data on spiritual and educational activities using information and communication technologies is of great importance.

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